

THE MODERATING EFFECT OF MOTIVATION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB BURNOUT AND JOB PERFORMANCE

NI NYOMAN SRI RAHAYU DAMAYANTI¹, I MADE ANDIKA PRADNYANA WISTAWAN², I GEDE NANDYA OKTORA PANASEA³, KOMANG ADI KURNIAWAN SAPUTRA⁴, I PUTU INDRA PERMANA WISTAWAN⁵, L.G.P. SRI EKA JAYANTI⁶

^{1,4,6} Warmadewa University, Bali, Indonesia

^{2,3} Udayana University, Bali, Indonesia

⁵The Audit Board of the Republic of Indonesia

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6552318

ABSTRACT

The research aims to know the effect of job burnout on job performance with motivation as the banking industry's moderator variable. BRI is the most significant profit bank in Indonesia and has more than 100.000.000 customers until the end of 2018. A large number of customers can increase the occurrence of job burnout in their employees. This condition will improve their work pressure and workload. Much research focused on job burnout and job performance, but the results are inconsistent. Due to the inconsistent effect, motivation can be used as the moderation variable in this research. The data analyzed by moderated regression analysis. The study respondents are the account officer and the funding officer who worked at BRI Renon Branch Office. The result showed that job burnout had a negative and significant influence on job performance. Motivation had a substantial impact on the relationship between job burnout and job performance. The banking industry implication that they can use it as a consideration to concern about any [aspects of motivation given to](#) employees [to minimize](#) the negative impact of job burnout.

Keywords: Job Burnout, Motivation, and Job Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The Bank industry is an organization that has an important part of a country. Bank also takes an integral role in public welfare. A bank is an institution that collects idle money temporarily from the public and lends it to other people as per need. Bank has several products, such as loans, savings, and deposits. They also can distribute the fund that already collected from the people to the other people who need them (Atmadja & Saputra, 2018). All products that offer to the public, hoping that the institution will profit from the interest and administration income. The institution offering and collecting funds must refer to the Bank of Indonesia (BI) regulations. The employees that take part to offer the products and analyze the customer financing proposal in a bank industry called account officers and funding officers. Jusup (1997) stated that the board assigned an account officer in handling the loan. The account officers are people who connect the bank and the loan customer. The account officers must seek, assess, evaluate, and propose the final customer financing proposal to the supervisor. The supervisor will check

it and offer it to the branch leader. Not only that, they have to control the [customer](#) periodically until they [complete](#) their obligations. On the other hand, a funding officer has to look for a customer who has idle money to be willing to save it in the form of products [offered by the bank](#) industry.

Both account officers and funding officers have a fundamental duty in the bank industry. The target given to them will slowly increase their workloads and work pressure. A high workload and work pressure will increase the probability of job burnout. Gorji (2011) stated that job burnout reflects emotional fatigue, body fatigue, and lack of energy that can negatively impact individual performance. Job burnout also makes people more pessimistic in facing their job to make a negative thought about their job. The lack of energy will interfere with the concentration of the employees when they were doing their situation. The employees will often do mistakes. The study takes place at Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI). BRI is the most significant profit bank in the Indonesian banking industry and always grows up to 2017 (bri.co.id, 2018). BRI public expose report in 2018 showed that BRI has a high number of customers. BRI has more than 100.000.000 customers until the end of 2018 (www.ir-bri.com, 2018). This condition will [increase the occurrence of job](#) burnout of their employees and decrease individual performance. Job performance consists of the observable behaviors that people do in their jobs relevant to the organization's goals (Campbell et al. 1990). Job performance is of interest to organizations because of the importance of high workplace productivity (Hunter & Hunter, 1984). The job performance of their employees can influence the performance of an organization. The better the performance, the bigger the probability of an organization can reach its goals.

There had been much research that focused on job burnout and performance. Badri (2017) found that job burnout had a negative and significant influence on performance. The same Nugroho et al. (2016) found that job burnout had a negative and significant impact on employee performance. On the other hand, Maharani and Triyoga (2012) found that job burnout had no significant influence on job performance. This inconsistency indicates [the presence of a contingent variable](#) affecting [the relationship between](#) job burnout and job performance. Motivation is used as a moderation variable in this research. Motivation is an encouragement for someone to do something. When one has a high level of motivation, he will have encouragement and desire to do the work. Richard (2014) states that motivation has a vital role in organizing employees to work effectively and efficiently according to their positions. The high motivated individual will perform better in work than the low motivated individual and will directly influence the employees' productivity in their works (Waiyaki, 2017)

Literature Review

Personality Theory

Personality theories concern the factors that determine and explain different individuals' personalities as they are and the factors which have brought about the given nature. Personality theory states that behavior can be known by understanding the three main components of personality: basic tendencies, characteristic adaptations, and self-concepts, as well as three supporting elements, namely biological basics, objective biography, and external influences. Personality theory states that one can predict how others will act based on the personality. This theory shows that behavior is determined by one's personality (Feist and Feist, 2009: 430). Alwisol (2009) states that personality is a general trait in thoughts, activities, and feelings that affect a person systemically. The nature of his personality will influence a person's reaction, and in this study, performance is the behavior that will later be affected by job burnout and motivation, which is placed as personality traits. The nature of one's personality determines the way the individual behaves.

Job Performance

Job performance is the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioral episodes that an individual carries out over a standard period. One important idea in this definition is that performance is a property of *behavior* (Saputra et al., 2020). In particular, it is an aggregated property of multiple, discrete actions that occur over some time. The second important idea is that the capital of behavior to which performance refers is its expected value to the organization. Thus, the performance construct by this definition is a variable that distinguishes between sets of actions carried out by different individuals and between sets of actions carried out by the same individual at different times.

Cook (2008) argues that an individual's performance is crucial because it influences an organization's productivity. The assessment of this aspect can be known from how someone manages the tasks and his desire to advance in his work field. Wright (1980) states four aspects of measuring performance: technical and analytical skills, interpersonal skills, communication skills, and professional characteristics.

Job Burnout

Job burnout happens due to the overwhelming feeling of exhaustion either physically, mentally, or emotionally, which causes a person to be distracted and decrease personal performance. Job burnout happens because of the working environment's characteristics, high work pressure, conflicts, the bottom of the formless control system, insufficient reward system, the disruption of the communication system, and the loss of justice in the workplace. Based on Maslach Multi Dimension Theory, there are three job burnout factors as follows.

1. Chronic exhaustion is a kind of tiredness that shows the base of individual tensions. Chronic exhaustion dimension is recognizable through physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion. The researcher showed that emotional exhaustion is the central quality of burnout and the most obvious manifestation of this complex syndrome.
2. Cynicism is related to the negative responses of the individuals because of a different working condition. That condition causes a feeling of being unacceptable, and finally, it makes a gap between the individuals and their jobs.
3. Lack of personal accomplishment refers to a decline in one's feelings of competence and achievement at work.

The first stage of Job burnout is physical burnout. This type of burnout is one of the constituents of the disability. A person who is exhausted complains about extreme boredom (often associated with insomnia). The person usually experiences signs indicating a lack of energy, chronic fatigue, and weakness. The second aspect of job burnout is emotional burnout. When a person's physical reserves are finished due to continued stressful job conditions, it may parallel that person's emotional force ends. Worker or employee who has lost his power and is exhausted expresses feelings such as depression, helplessness, and frustration by themselves. In these conditions, satisfaction that acquired before and at the time of leisure or beside family and friends' decreases, and as a result, the overall satisfaction with life decreases. The third aspect of job burnout is mental burnout. In this case, the worker deal with the negative view towards work, customers, or client of the organization and colleagues. The fact that such a person is exhausted and is not able to observe the feelings and needs of others indicate that his dealing is free of humanitarian aspects (Tayyebi & Mina, 2017)

Based on the literature review of job burnout, here it is the first hypothesis as follows.

H₁: Job burnout has a negative effect on job performance.

Motivation

Motivation is divided into two definitions; conceptually and operationally. Conceptually, working motivation is defined as one of the factors influencing the performance of someone. The size or effect of motivation on one's performance depends on how much intensity the motivation is given. Operationally, work motivation is defined as the drive from inside and outside of a person to do something visible from the internal and external dimensions. Maduka and Okafor (2014) stated that motives could be in the form of individual needs and desires. The motive will encourage someone to act, which will determine the behavior in question. In the workplace, a reward given to the employee is one kind of motivation used in an organization. A reward is given to the employees that had to reach their target. On the other hand, promotion of position is one kind of motivation too. It depends on the organization in choosing the form of motivation to be given. Individuals with a high level of motivation will increase company productivity. They tend to be more concerned, more effective, and efficient in finishing their task to produce a good performance. [They are also more excited](#) about working [because](#) some motives are their [background](#) and encouragement, [whether it is an incentive, promotion, promotions, and other](#) positions. Motivation trusted can weaken the negative effect on the relationship between job burnout and job performance. Based on the literature review of motivation, here is the second hypothesis as follows.

H₂: Motivation as the moderating variable on the relationship between job burnout and job performance.

Methodology

The research population was the account officer and funding officer who worked at Bank Rakyat Indonesia Renon Branch Office. This study used the saturated sample technique, which included the entire population as a sample of as many as 32 people. The data collection method used in this study was the survey method with questionnaire techniques. First of all, the Method of Successive Interval (MSI) was carried out on the answers to the questionnaires that have been filled in by the respondents. The MSI process was carried out to transform ordinal data (questionnaire scores) into interval data. After that, the research instrument was tested by testing the validity and reliability. If the correlation coefficient is at least 0.3, then the instrument has been declared valid. If Cronbach's alpha is more than 0.60, it means that the instrument used is reliable (Nunnally, 1960 in Ghazali, 2009: 46). After all of the instruments are valid and reliable, the next analysis is a classical assumption test. There are two kinds of classical assumption tests used in this research, and there are a normality test and heteroscedasticity test. If the asymp.sig (2-tailed) value of the normality test is greater than 0,05, and it means that the distribution data is normal. The same with the heteroscedasticity test, when the asymp.sig (2-tailed) value greater than 0,05, which means that the data already free from heteroscedasticity problem. The last analysis is to test the hypothesis by using moderated regression analysis. Moderated Regression [Analysis](#) (MRA) [or interaction test](#) is [a special application of multiple linear](#) regression, [Wherein a regression equation](#) contains [element](#) interactions ([multiplication of two or more independent variables](#)).

Based on the data obtained, most of the respondents were male. The majority of the respondents aged between 31 to 40 years old. All of the respondents had followed some training held by Bank Rakyat Indonesia. The training usually implements once a year and takes place at Surabaya Regency. Most of the account officer and funding officer had worked for more than 3 years in their position. All of the instruments are valid with correlation coefficient values greater than 0.3. All of the instruments are

reliable, with the value of Cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.60. The result showed that all of the instruments could be used for further research.

Data distribution was normal with asymp.sig (2-tailed) value of 0.450. The heteroscedasticity test was done by Glejser test, which regresses the residual absolute value from the model estimated on the independent variable with the value of job burnout is 0,059. The result means that the data had free from the heteroscedasticity problem and can be used for the hypothesis test.

Data distribution was normal with asymp.sig (2-tailed) value of 0.901. The heteroscedasticity test was done by Glejser test to regress the residual absolute value from the model estimated on the independent variable. The value of job burnout and motivation are 0,743 and 0,747. The result means that the data already free from the heteroscedasticity problem.

Results and Discussion

The effect of job burnout on job performance of account officer

The result showed that the significance value of job burnout is 0,004 and the B value of -0,322. It means that job burnout had a negative and significant effect on job performance. Bank Rakyat Indonesia is the largest profit bank in the Indonesian banking industry and always grows up to 2017 (bri.co.id, 2018). BRI public expose report in 2018 showed that BRI has a high number of customers. BRI has more than 100.000.000 customers until the end of 2018 (www.ir-bri.com, 2018). BRI profit, one of which comes from loan interest. A high number of loan applications reflected a high responsibility of the account officer to finished the analysis well. After analyzing the application, the account officer has to maintain the customer until the loan is repaid. On the other hand, the funding officer has a great responsibility too. They have to seek funds to be placed at the bank. They have a high target of funds that have to be placed in a bank in a year. The funding officer targeted to seek for the customer who makes new savings account. When both account officers and funding officers cannot reach the target given to them, it will be difficult for them to manage the promotion to the next grade. They will also get a poor performance rating, so getting a reward, whether incentives promotions of position and others becomes very small.

This condition makes high work pressure on the employees in the workplace. It is feared that the condition cause job burnout. Job individual characteristics of the working environment can cause burnout, high work pressure, conflicts, less control system, insufficient reward system, the disruption of the communication system, and the loss of justice in the workplace. The condition makes individuals have a low concentration at the workplace. They will have a low encouragement to finish their job. A person who has job burnout and self-respect descends, his relationships disappear, and he may feel that too many works and cannot control his much work. He knows himself as a swimmer against the water moves and cannot keep his head above water. This condition causes a person's sense of hopelessness and helplessness. All of those characteristics will make a negative effect on their job performance. The negative effect is not only felt at the workplace but also at home and in social life.

The effect of job burnout on job performance with motivation as the moderating variable

The result showed that the significance value of 0,014 and the B value of -0,31. It means that motivation can be used as a moderator variable on the relationship between job burnout and job performance. From the result, motivation weakened the negative effect of job burnout on job performance. Individual characteristics of the working environment can cause job Top of Form

burnout, high work pressure, conflicts, less control system, insufficient reward system, the disruption of the communication system, and the loss of justice in the workplace. Operationally, work motivation is defined as the drive from inside and outside of a person to do something. Motivation will encourage someone to act to reach their goal. Extrinsic motivation is a kind of incentive or reward from external sides, such as money, promotion, recognition, career opportunities, and others. In other words, it is something usually tangible, or a purpose that comes needs to be chased by an employee. Most of the respondents are married and have a family. They have a responsibility to support his family with funds. This motive also makes them stay at their job and face every problem and task given to them. Individuals with high motivation can manage their tasks well because they have a strong background and strong encouragement to finish their job. When they can finish it well, they will have a high conviction that they will get a reward. Those conditions can make motivation weakened the negative effect of job burnout on job performance.

1. CONCLUSION,

The results showed that job burnout had a negative and significant effect on job performance. Motivation can be used as a moderator variable on the relationship between job burnout and job performance. Motivation weakened the negative effect of job burnout on job performance.

The implication of the research for the education sector is that they can use this research as a reference, especially in individual behavior. For the banking industry, they can use it as a consideration to be more concerned about any aspects of motivation given to the employees to minimize the negative impact of job burnout on performance. It will be a consideration for the banking industry in making a regulation about the motivation for their employees, such as regulation in giving a reward, promotion of positions, and many more.

Subsequent research can use the account officer and funding officer in more branch offices as the respondents of the research to get a better generalization.

The limitations of the research are that the respondents conducted their assessment of their performance. This is feared to result in a subjective judgment.

REFERENCES

Alwisol. 2009. *Psikologi Kepribadian Edisi Revisi*. Malang: UMM Press.

Atmadja, A. T., & Saputra, K. A. K. (2018). The influence of role conflict, the complexity of an assignment, role obscurity, and locus of control on internal auditor performance. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 22(5), 1-5.

Badri, N.A.H.A. 2017. "Hubungan Burnout dengan Kinerja di Kalangan Pustakawan Universitas Indonesia" (*tesis*). Surabaya: Universitas Airlangga

Bank BRI. 2018. Raup Laba Rp. 23,5 Triliun, Efisiensi dan FBI Topang Kinerja BRI di Triwulan III 2018. <http://bri.co.id>. 21 Maret 2019 (19:30)

Campbell. J. P., and Campbell, R. J., 1990, productivity in organizations. San Fransisco: Josey-Bass Publisher.

Cook, A. L., 2008. "Job Satisfaction and Job Performance: Is the Relationship Spurious" (*tesis*). Texas: Texas A&M University.

- Feist, Jess dan Feist, Gregory J. 2009. *Theories of Personality*. Amerika Serikat: McGraw Hill.
- Gorji, M. (2011). The Effect of Job Burnout Dimension on Employees' Performance. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 1(4), 243–246. <https://doi.org/10.7763/ijssh.2011.v1.43>
- Ghozali, Imam. 2009. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program SPSS*. Edisi Kedua. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro.
- Jusuf, Jopie. Panduan dasar untuk Account Officer. 1997. Yogyakarta: Akademi Manajemen Perusahaan YKPN.
- Leiter, M. P., and Maslach, C., 1998. The Impact of Interpersonal Environment of Burnout and Organization Commitment. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, Vol. 9: 297-308.
- Maduka C.E and Okafor O. 2014. "Effect of Motivation on Employee Productivity: A Study of Manufacturing Companies in Nnewi." *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*. Vol. 2:7
- Maharani, P.A, & Triyoga, A. Kejenuhan Kerja (Burnout) Dengan Kinerja Perawat Dalam Pemberian Asuhan Keperawatan. *Jurnal STIKES*, Volume 5, No. 2, Desember 2012.
- Nugroho, H. R., Susilo, H., & Iqbal, M. (2016). *Pengaruh Job Burnout dan Kepuasan Kerja Melalui Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan*. 37(2), 173–182.
- Saputraa, K. A. K., Subrotob, B., Fuad, A., & Rahmanc, E. S. (2020). Issues of Morality and Whistleblowing in Short Prevention Accounting. *Int. J. Innov. Creat. Chang*, 12(3), 77-88.
- Tayyebi, R. A. D. R., & Mina, J. (2017). *Investigate the Most Important Causes of Job Burnout of Employees (Case Study : Youth and Sports General Directorate of Qom)*. (3), 167–174.
- Trisnaningsih, S. 2007. Independensi Auditor dan Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Mediasi Pengaruh Pemahaman Good Governance, Gaya Kepemimpinan dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Auditor. *Simposium Nasional Akuntansi X*. Makassar, 26-28 Juli.
- Waiyaki, E.W., 2017. "Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance: A Case of Pam Golding Properties Limited, Nairobi" (*tesis*). Nairobi: United States International University.
- Wright. A. 1980. Performance Appraisal of Staff Auditors. *The CPA Journal*, Vol. 50: 37-43.